

Effect of Technical Education in Food and Beverage for Sustainable Economic Development in Covid 19 Era in Baringo Technical College, Kenya

Ogweyo Peter Ogalo^{1*}, Robert Maina Aminga²

¹Baringo Technical College

²University of Eldoret

*Corresponding author email: peterogwey48@gmail.com

Published online: 9th September, 2023

Abstract

Food and beverage sectors play major roles in the economic sector, and it has attracted many youths who want to learn how to bake cakes and cook local and international dishes. The study purposed to Establish Model of Sustainable Economic Development out of Technical skills, blended learning and Resource Challenges from the first three objectives which were; to establish significance relationship between Technical Skills in food and Beverage on Sustainable Economic Development, To Find out Relationship between Training Methods and Sustainable Economic Development in food and beverage and establish the relationship between Resource Challenges on sustainable economic development in food and beverage. The research adopted quantitative method and approximated population of 100 and sample size of 80. The null hypotheses were rejected; there was significance relationship between the variable. The variables were modelled using regression model to establish the relationship between the variables. The results showed that there was negative contribution of technical skills (B= -4.409) and Blended learning (B= -2.003) towards contribution of sustainable economic development. However, Resource Changes showed positive contribution (B=-.150) Towards Sustainable economic development. The study outcomes concluded that technical skills and blended learning contributed negatively on sustainable economic development. More studies on the aspects of Technical Education in Food and Beverage in relationship to sustainable economic development Study further on sustainable development goal 4 and food and beverage sectors The was need for curriculum to capture aspects of sustainable economic development and sustainable development goals.

Key words: Technical Education, Food and Beverage, Sustainable Economic Development, Covid 19 Era.

Introduction

The complex relationships in economic development with a focus on the context in which universities operate socio-economic development, the internal structure and dynamics of the universities, and the interaction between national and institutional contexts have recently been studied (Grant, 2017). Common to the success of all these systems is, amongst others, the link between economic and educational planning; quality public schooling; high tertiary participation rates with institutional differentiation; labour market demand; cooperation and networks; and consensus about the importance of Higher Education for education and development (Grant, 2017). There was, however, an increasing awareness, particularly at government level, of the importance of universities in the global context of the knowledge economy (Grant 2017). A number of the universities had manageable student staff ratios and adequately qualified staff, but inadequate funds for staff to engage in research.

The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the International Labour Organization (ILO) recommendations of 2000 on technical and vocational education and training for the twenty-first century, defined TVET as those aspects of education process involving, in addition, to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life (Ajibola, 2012)

Human capital has long been thought of the foremost disposition of the national economy and more work has proved the impact of education on productivity growth through (Grant 2017). Available estimates on the social and private rates of return to investment in primary education are the highest, followed by secondary education. Returns to higher education are the least. Such evidence is extensively used to discourage public investment in Higher Education and to concentrate almost exclusively on primary education in the 1980s and 1990s (Grant 2017). Education could be a leading determinant of economic process, employment, and earnings. Ignoring the economic dimension of education would endanger the prosperity of future generations, with widespread repercussions for financial condition, social exclusion, and property of social insurance systems (Franz, 2016). TVET is understood as comprising education, training and skills development relating to a wide range of occupational fields, production, services and livelihoods (Okwori, Yisa, and Mustapha 2021). Then all of a sudden people were forced to stay at home, keep social distance and sanitize frequently. Due to population growth and urbanization; poverty and lack of income

generating capacity and failure of graduates from schools' system to secure employment clearly highlighted the importance of career development which is achievable through TVET. The main challenges in implementing online learning for TVET were development of technology, infrastructure and human resource, and management, economic and policy issues. However, the effectiveness of pedagogy approaches and assessment methods in online learning are seldom discussed (M. Nasir, 2020). With the current educational practices and technological development, other online learning integration such as application of software and hardware in online learning, social media networks, and webinars also need to be considered (M. Nasir, 2020)

Low quality training: In general, the quality of training is low, with undue emphasis on theory and certification rather than skill acquisition and proficiency testing. Inadequate instructor training, inappropriate training equipment(demonstration equipment instead of actual equipment use in the industry), poor aspiration of incoming trainees, obnoxious policy of 80 percent success rate of trainees before accreditation of polytechnics and lack of instructional materials are some of the factors that combine to reduce the effectiveness of training in meeting the required knowledge and skill objectives(Ajibola, 2012). General education, theory and related courses, workshop practice, industrial training/production work and entrepreneurial training.

Trainees completing technical college programmes shall have three options: secure employment either at the end of whole course or after completing one or more modules of employable skills, set up their own businesses and become self-employed and be able to employ others and pursue further education i. Each programme or modules at technical colleges consists of entrepreneurial training which is an indication that the achievement of any of the goal of TVET at technical college level depends fully on the entrepreneurship knowledge of the students. Without entrepreneurship skills, one cannot be self-employed or be employable(Okwori, Yisa, and Mustapha 2021). At the institutional level, the Lockdown measures have led to the worldwide closure of TVET institutions and skills development organizations. As distance education and training becomes the norm, the ability of TVET institutions to implement such system depends on their capacity to adapt curricula as well as the preparedness of trainers and teachers. While at the systemic level the economic recession triggered by the COVID-19 crisis is causing a massive rise in unemployment and under-employment that could have a lasting impact on essential livelihoods. Transformations in the labour market will also result in changes in skills demands. TVET systems need to address

the short- and medium-term impact of the current pandemic by not only scaling up TVET solutions but also formulating responses that reflect long-term sustainability and effective(Okwori, Yisa, and Mustapha 2021). Types of teaching methods that could be use in this era of COVID-19 pandemic for effectiveness of entrepreneurship in TVET is student centred method that embraces e-learning or digital technology learning because they have been used by different researchers in different fields, such as: video tape instruction, video conferencing, blended learning, Edublogs, web-bases instruction, microblogs instruction and many more(Okwori, Yisa, and Mustapha 2021)

Specific objective

1. To establish significance Relationship between Technical Skills in Food and Beverage on Sustainable Economic Development,
2. To Find out Relationship between Training Methods on Sustainable Economic Development in Food and Beverage
3. To establish the relationship between Resource Challenges on Sustainable Economic development in Food and Beverage.
4. Establish Model of Sustainable Economic Development out of Technical skills, blended learning and Resource Challenges

Hypothesis

1. There was no significance Relationship between Technical Skills in Food and Beverage on Sustainable Economic Development,
2. There was no significance Relationship between Training Methods and Sustainable Economic Development in Food and Beverage
3. There was no significance relationship between Resource Challenges and Sustainable Economic development in Food and Beverage.

Scope of the Study

The study was based in Baringo Technical College focusing at Food and beverage graduates, who experienced online training and learning COVID Era. The relationship between that training sustainable economic development.

Research Methods

The chapter discussed design, population, sample size, method of data collection and ethical consideration

Research Design

The research design used in this study to be adopted was descriptive survey research design. States that the descriptive study is a method, which enabled the researcher to summarize and organize data in an effective and meaningful way (Nyakundi et al., 2014). According to Aborisade a descriptive survey research is concerned with finding out the what, where and how of a phenomenon (Aborisade, 2013). The study will be conducted in Baringo Technical College. Focussed at Graduates Who Experienced Online Training During Covid 19 Era. Sampling means selecting a given number of subjects from a defined population as representative of that population

Sampling Size

A sample is part of the target population that has been selected as a representative sample (Nyakundi et al., 2014). The study employed Yamane's formula for determination of the sample size n , which is given by:

$$:n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where: N is the total target population, e is the margin of error (or level of significance) n is the required sample size. Since the target population is 100 and taking the margin of error to be 0.05 (for 95% level of confidence), the study sample size worked out as follows

$$:n = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.05)^2}$$
$$=80$$

Hence, the sample size is 80 respondents. From the calculated sample size of 80 respondents, 10 were picked from trainers while 70 were selected from Food and Beverage trainees. The researcher stratified the five TVET institutions into diploma, certificate or artisan level training. Each of the three groups form a (strata). From each stratum, simple random sampling technique was used to select at least 50% of the trainees, using a sampling fraction of two. (Kasunic 2005)

Data collection Instruments

A questionnaire was developed by the researcher for collecting data in this study. A questionnaire is preferred to other instruments because of its economy in terms of time and labour for its administration (Creswell 2007). In this research it was chosen because it is interpersonal and hence allowed the subjects to give their answers anonymously (Creswell

2007). A questionnaire is an ideal instrument as it can gather descriptive information from a large sample in a fairly short time. Closed ended questionnaires were used.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration purpose to protect respondent’s information and maintain confidentiality, and the research will be used for academic purpose only. Consideration towards ethical issues will be given priority before and during research process. Respondents, research participants will be voluntarily involved for the study process without any kind of incentives, rewards and even motivations. Research

Results and Discussion

The chapter discussed gender, age and the results of the three objectives, hypothesis and model of sustainable economic development

Table 1: Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	23	32.4	32.4	32.4
	Female	48	67.6	67.6	100.0
	Total	71	100.0	100.0	

There were 32.4% male and 67.6% female. There were more females than males.

Table 2: Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	47	66.2	66.2	66.2
	26-35	24	33.8	33.8	100.0
	Total	71	100.0	100.0	

There were 66.2% in the age ranges from 18-25 and 26-35 were 33.8% the group with highest was due to their energetic ability that food and beverage sectors required

Table 3 Relationship Between Technical Skills and Sustainable Economic Development

		Sustainable economic development	Technical skills
Sustainable economic development	Pearson Correlation	1	-.470**

	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	70	70
Technical skills	Pearson Correlation	-.470**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	70	72

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance relationship between technical skills sustainable economic development

The relationship between technical skills and sustainable economic development was negative as established table 3 above

That the relationship was -.470 which was the statistical significance. From the table the probability significance (P value) was .000 which was less than .05 which implied that increased of technical skills statistically significantly predicted decreased in contributing towards sustainable economic development. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 4 Relationship Between Training Methods and Sustainable Economic Development

		Sustainable economic development	Training Methods
Sustainable economic development	Pearson Correlation	1	.113
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	72	72
Training Methods	Pearson Correlation	.113	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	72	72

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance relationship between training methods and sustainable economic development

The relationship between training methods and sustainable economic development was positive as established by the beta coefficient of .113 in table 4 above. Showed that training methods contributed positively towards sustainable economic development by .113. The significance level from the (P value) was .000 which was less than .05 which implied that increases of training methods statistically significantly predicted that there was increase in sustainable economic development to graduates. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5 Relationship Between Resource Challenges and Sustainable Economic Development

		Sustainable economic development	Resource Challenges
Sustainable economic development	Pearson Correlation	1	.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	72	72
Resource Challenges	Pearson Correlation	.146	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

Hypothesis 3: There was no significance relationship between Resources Challenges and sustainable economic development

The relationship between Resources Challenges and sustainable economic development was positive as established by the beta coefficient of .146 in table 5 above. Therefore, Resources led to increase in the sustainable economic development by .146. From the table the probability significance (P value) was .000 which was less than .05 which implied that increases of Resource challenges statistically significantly predicted there was significant relationship to sustainable economic development. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6 Regression Model of Sustainable Economic Development

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	46.673	6.570		7.104	.000
	Technical Skills	-4.409	.862	-.691	-5.114	.000
	Blended learning	-2.003	.917	-.301	-2.184	.032
	Resource Challenges	.150	.093	.169	1.612	.112

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable economic development

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

Y_1 - Sustainable Economic Development.

X_1 -Technical skills

X_2 - Blended Learning

X_3 - Resource Challenges

Sustainable Economic development =

$$Y_1 = 46.673 - 4.409X_1 - 2.003X_2 + 0.150X_3 + \epsilon$$

The variables were modelled using regression model to establish the relationship between the variables. The results showed that there was negative contribution of technical skills (B= -4.409) and Blended learning (B= -2.003) towards contribution of sustainable economic development. However, Resource Changes showed positive contribution (B=.150) Towards Sustainable economic development. The study outcomes concluded that technical skills and blended learning contributed negatively on sustainable economic development. Therefore, the training department should only focus at working on the challenges to solve Resources challenges. Therefore, the sustainable development goal 8 which advocated for the efficient employment for economic development. There due limited resources made graduates creative to enhance sustainable economic development.

Conclusions and Recommendations

There was significance relationship between the variable contributing to sustainable economic development. The relationship between Resources Challenges and sustainable economic development was negative. The relationship between training methods and sustainable economic development was positive. The relationship between technical skills and sustainable economic development was negative

Recommendations

1. According to finding there is need to conduct further study to establish how resource challenges contributed to sustainable economic development
2. There is need to conduct research to investigate aspects of training methods which contributed negatively towards sustainable economic development
3. To conduct a study on the relationship between Technical skills on employability of graduates
4. Study further on blended learning and sectors such as Building, Agriculture, in relationship to sustainable economic development
5. More studies on the aspects of Technical Education in Food and Beverage in relationship to sustainable economic development
6. Study further on sustainable development goal 4 and food and beverage sectors

7. The was need for curriculum to capture aspects of sustaianble economic development and sustainable development goals

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